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EXAMINATION OF LONG TERM EFFECT OF EXCHANGE RATE ON INDIAN STOCK MARKET

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the long run relation among Stock Returns and four major Foreign Exchanges in India over a period of 14 ½ year period starting from January, 2000 to June, 2014. On applying the techniques of Unit-root test, Multiple Break Point test, Johansen's Cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model, the result suggest that US dollar and Euro has long-term relation with Sensex, Nifty and CNX 500 which was found statistically significant. Tests depict no long term cointegration with GBP and Yen.

Keywords: BSE, NIFTY, CNX 500, VECM, Johansen Cointegration and Foreign Exchange.

JEL classification: E44, G1.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Foreign Exchange market is the lubricant that enables companies to use different currencies to trade with each other. Exchange rate exposures can impact on a firm's profit and may affect the stock returns. Lot of studies is carried on to know the impact on exchange rate fluctuations on stock returns. One such study done by Reinhart and Rogoff (2004) identifies that Indian currency was pegged to US dollar from 1979-2001, which provides an evidence that stock returns depends on exchange³.

Exchange rates can affect stock prices not only for multinational and export-oriented units but also for domestic companies. For a multinational, changes in exchange rates will result in an immediate change in value of its foreign operations which in turn reflects in its income statements. Therefore, the changes in economic value of firm's foreign operations may influence stock prices. Domestic firms can also be influenced by changes in exchange rates since they may import a part of their inputs and export their outputs. Thus, evaluation will make positive effect for export firms⁴ and increase the income of these firms, consequently, boosting the average level of stock prices⁵. Thus, understanding this relationship will help domestic as well as international investors.

Globalisation has increased the cross border movement of funds with the world moving towards a free trade zone. The technological development in the field of communication, trading systems and introduction of innovative financial products has helped the investors to face today's challenges to maximise their returns by portfolio investments. On the other hand, emerging market economies have turned the corner and recovered sharply but a lot still needs to be done for realizing developed markets. Therefore, it is very essential for both investors and academicians to know whether stock markets are dependent. The issue is also important for policy makers for the following reason: if stock markets are found to be closely linked then there is a danger that stocks in one market will spill over to the other markets too.

One of the purposes of this study is to examine price discovery between the Sensex, Nifty, CNX 500 and foreign exchange market using cointegration analysis which offers several advantages. First, cointegration analysis measures the extent to which two markets have achieved long run equilibrium. Another distinct advantage of the cointegration technique is that it explicitly allows for divergences from equilibrium in the short run.

2. Review of Literature

1. Bahmani and Sohrabiab (1992) reported that there is no long term relationship between stock prices and exchanges rates in the U.S.A. However, they reported a short term relationship between these two variables using Granger Causality tests.
2. Abdalla and Murinde (1997) employed a BVAR model to examine the stock price interaction with exchange rates in four countries. They concluded that exchange rates Granger cause stock prices to change in India, Pakistan and Korea. However, they did not find any relationship between stock prices and exchange rates in the Philippines.

³ Reinhart CM, Rogoff KS (2004):"The Modern History of Exchange Rate Arrangements: A Reinterpretation." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 119(1), 1-48p.

⁴ Aggarwal, R. (2003). Exchange rates and stock prices: A study of the US capital markets under floating exchange rates. *Akron Business and Economic Review*- 12, 7-12p.

⁵ Wu, Y. (2000). Stock prices and exchange rates in a VEC model-the case of Singapore in the 1990s. *Journal of Economics and Finance*-24(3), 260-274p.

3. Apte (2001) in a study incorporates asymmetric affects of positive and negative returns surprises on volatility both in the same market as well as spillovers across the two markets. Empirical analysis with one of the major stock market indices supports the hypothesis of such volatility linkages while for the other index there appears to be a spillover from the foreign exchange market to the stock market but not the other way round.
4. Adjasi, Harvey and Agyapong (2008) in their study find the relationship between stock market and macroeconomic variables statistically significant. Furthermore suggest volatility persistence in most of the macroeconomic variables. Further the study revealed that an increase or decrease in trade deficit and expectation in future rise in trade deficit will decrease or increase stock market volatility.
5. Noel, John & John (2009) in their paper examine the interaction between stock prices and exchange rates in Australia. During the period of the study, the value of the stock market increased by two-thirds and the Australian dollar exchange rate appreciated by almost one-third. The empirical analysis provides a positive co-integrating relationship between these variables, with Granger causality found to run from stock prices to the exchange rate during the sample period.
6. Kumar Sundaram (2009) examines that there is no long-run equilibrium relationship and causality relationship between stock returns and exchange rates. Furthermore, finds that FII gives positive unidirectional Granger causality results and no reverse i.e. stock returns Granger cause FII. No reverse causality is seen even after inserting a structural break in 2003, as some of the researchers suggest.
7. Shekar, Malaabika & Hamad (2010) explores one dynamic relationship between stock return and forex rate by testing co integration & Granger causality test, the study period reports unidirectional relationship among forex rate and stock return except in the year 2009 because of bivariate causality between both the markets.
8. Gaurav, Aniruddh, Ankita (2010) found that Nifty returns as well as exchange rates were non-normally distributed. Through Unit Root test, it was also established that exchange rate and Nifty returns, were stationary at the level form itself. Correlation between Nifty returns and Exchange Rates was found to be negative. Further investigation into the causal relationship between the two variables using Granger Causality test highlighted unidirectional relationship between Nifty returns and Exchange Rates, running from the former towards the latter.
9. Gopalan Kutty (2010) shows that there is some short run relationship between stock prices and exchange rates. The Granger causality tests reveals that stock prices lead exchange rates in the short run, and there is no long run relationship between these two financial variables. One of the practical implications of this study is that policy makers of the Mexican economy should be cautious in implementing or taking stock market regulation or policies since it has short term implication on exchange rates.
10. Srinivasan (2011) explores the long-run relationships between NSE-Nifty share price index and the index of industrial production, money supply, interest rate, exchange rate, consumer price index and US stock price index. The empirical results reveal that the NSE-Nifty share price index has a significant positive long-run relationship with money supply, interest rate, index of industrial production and the US stock market index. Further, there exists a significant negative relationship between the NSE-Nifty share price index and exchange rate in the long run. Moreover, there is a significant short-run causality between a few monetary variables like money supply and interest rate, inflation and money supply, and the US stock market and exchange rate.
11. Vanitha & Namita (2014) find that existence of long term relationship among Forex, oil price and stock market. Lagged stock returns have a statistically negative influence on exchange rate

returns during the global financial crisis period, however stock returns in India are not affected significantly by either the oil price or exchange rate. Further, stock market pulls the oil market in India. Hence, unidirectional causality from stock market to oil market exists. If the stock prices get trapped in a bubble, however, oil price will overshoot in relation to economic fundamentals.

Summary of Literature Review

Sl. No	Authors	Data-Country	Estimation Method
1	Bahmani and Sohrabiab (1992)	US	VECM & Granger causality tests.
2	Abdalla and Murinde (1997)	India, Korea, Pakistan and Philippines	BVAR & Granger causality tests.
3	Apte (2001)	India	Descriptive stats & E-Garch
4	Charles Adjasi, Simon K. Harvey and Daniel Agyapong (2008)	Ghana	ADF, Cointegration, GARCH, EGARCH
5	Noel, John & John (2009)	Australia	Cointegration & Granger Causality
6	Kumar Sundaram (2009)	Indian	Structural Breaks, cointegration, VECM & Causality.
7	Shekar, Malaabika & Hamad (2010)	India	ADF, Cointegration and Granger causality test
8	Gaurav, Aniruddh, Ankita (2010)	India	Cointegration and Granger Causality
9	Gopalan Kutty (2010)	Mexico	Cointegration, VECM and Granger causality
10	Srinivasan (2011)	US	Cointegration, VECM & causality
11	Vanitha & Namita (2014)	India	Unit root test, Cointegration, VECM and Causality.

3. Sources

3.1 Basic Data:

This study examines the foreign exchange effect on Indian stock market. In this regard, Stock returns were logged and measured using the daily closing prices of the stock index. For calculating stock returns BSE and NSE stock indices were chosen, representing BSE 30, CNX Nifty & CNX500.

3.2 To calculate stock index returns:

$$\text{Daily Rate of Return} = \ln(P_t / P_{t-1}) * 100$$

Where $\ln P_t$ is the natural log of closing Index of the day, and

$\ln P_{t-1}$ is the natural log of closing Index of yesterday

3.3 Foreign Exchange:

In case of exchange rate, daily Rupee v/s US dollar, Great Britain Pound, EURO & Japanese Yen exchange rate are considered for the study, closing market values are gathered from the Reserve Bank of India. The exchange rate is expressed in terms of the number of Rupee per unit of US dollar, Great Britain Pound, EURO & in case of yen, *per hundred* is considered for the study.

The exchange rates are expressed by USD, GBP, and Euro & Yen. The symbols stand for USD=US dollar, GBP=Great Britain Pounds, Euro= currency used by the Institutions of the European Union &

Yen= Japanese Yen per hundred. Both sets of data are synchronized & ensured that the trading days of both time-series matched. The study was conducted for a period of 14 ½ years starting from January, 2000 to June, 2014.

There are total of 3,497 observations representing all the trading days gathered and analyzed using Ms excel & EViews statistical package.

4. Methodology & Research objective:

Recent studies in the time series analysis have suggested some improvements in testing time series data. The first step is to check for the stationarity of the original variables, then check for structural breaks and then test cointegration among them.

For the purpose of this study, the following tests were conducted- Multiple break point tests as per Bai-Perron for structural breaks, Unit root test, JB test, Johansen and Juselius cointegration test & Vector Error Correction Model.

4.1 Multiple Breakpoint Test:

Modern studies indicate that structural changes in financial econometrics have greater scope and are a part of regression models. Various studies such as Chow test (1960), Quandt (1960), Andrews (1993) and more recently, Bai & Perron (1998, 2003) state the effect of break dates on overall model specification. In this study, multiple break point test were applied on Sensex, Nifty & CNX 500 and were tested as per Bai & Perron.

4.2 Lag Length:

A successful model depends on right number of lags, if too many lags are included then model becomes ineffective and estimators becomes inefficient. So it is essential to define comprehensive model. In this study, lag length was considered on the basis of Information Criteria tests based on LR, FPE & AIC.

4.3 Stationary Test & Unit root:

Stationary of a series is a stochastic process and plays very vital role in time series, as it influences ordinary least square and generates spurious regression. It is process of checking mean & variance over a period of time and if mean and variance of a series is constant over a period of time then the variables are set to be stationary and ready for further statistical test and model building.

There are several methods for testing Unit root presence. This study adopts widely used Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

$$\text{ADF equation: } \Delta Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 t + \delta Y_{t-1} + \alpha_i \sum_{i=1}^m \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Augment is applied when the error term (ε_t) are correlated & (Δ) is the first difference operator. Otherwise Dickey Fuller test can be used. The hypothesis for this test is

$H_0 : \delta = 0$ i.e. time series is non stationery

$H_1: \delta = 1$ i.e. time series is stationery

4.4 Cointegration Test:

This test checks for linear combination of order of integration & long run movement among the following variables:

- 1) Sensex, USD, GBP, Euro and Yen.

- 2) Nifty, USD, GBP, Euro and Yen.
- 3) CNX 500, USD, GBP, Euro and Yen

In this study we have used Johansen’s Cointegration test.

As per Johansen’s Cointegration test, if the set of variables are of I(1) order then they should not be estimated using OLS, but the number of cointegrating vectors has to be estimated. If the set of variables are Cointegrated then VECM (Vector Error Correction Model) adjusts to both short run changes in variables and deviations from equilibrium.

$$Y_t = A_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p A_j Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon$$

Where Y_t is an $n \times 1$ vector of non stationary I(1) variables, A_0 is an $n \times 1$ vector of constants, p is the number of lags, A_j is a $(n \times n)$ matrix of coefficients and is assumed to be a $(n \times 1)$ vector of Gaussian error terms.

Inference on Cointegration test can be made out of likelihood ratio test or trace statistic. ε

$$TRACE = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^n (1 - \lambda_i) \quad r = 0 \dots n - 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_{\max} = -T \text{LOG}(1 - \lambda_{r+1}) \quad r = 0 \dots n - 1 \quad (2)$$

Here T is the sample size and λ_i is the i^{th} largest canonical correlation. This tests the hypothesis that the number of Cointegrating vectors is at the most $r(H_0: r = 0)$ against the alternative hypothesis which is greater than $r(H_0: r \geq 0)$ co integrating vectors and the maximal- Eigen value test (lambda-max) hypothesis that number of cointegrating vectors = r against the alternative that it is $r+1$ cointegrating vectors.

4.5 Vector Auto Regression (VECM)

If the variables under study found to have one or more co integrating vector (s), then VECM is the suitable technique which adjusts to both short run changes in variables and deviations from equilibrium. In this study three different stock indices and four foreign exchanges are considered as endogenous variables.

4.6 Research objective:

- i. To determine cointegration among the variables.
- ii. To find Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

5. Result and Analysis

Results are presented in order of three variable orders and all testing were conducted using EViews statistical software.

5.1 Multiple break point tests

As our data examines for last 14 ½ years, it is essential for any time series to ascertain several structural breaks. A structural break occurs when the estimated parameters in the model are unstable over time period. To determine the multiple breakpoints between the periods Bai-Perron test is performed.

Table –1 depicts the result among the variables

Bai-Perron tests of L+1 vs. L sequentially determined breaks.
Break test options: Trimming 0.15, Max. breaks 5, Sig. level 0.05

Test statistics employ HAC covariances (Prewhitening with lags= 1
 Quadratic-Spectral kernel, Andrews bandwidth)
 Allows heterogeneous error distributions across breaks

	SENSEX	NIFTY	CNX 500
Break Test	0 vs. 1	0 vs. 1	0 vs. 1
F-statistic	4.442701	3.753884	3.449961
Scaled F-statistic	4.442701	3.753884	3.449961
Critical Value at 5%	8.58	8.58	8.58
Sequential Breaks	0	0	0
As per Bai-Perron (Econometric Journal, 2003) critical values.			

Interpretation:

The above table shows F-statistic along with the F-statistic scaled by the number of varying regressors and the Bai-Perron critical value for the scaled statistic. Here sequential test indicates that there are no breakpoints and the test does not reject the null against 0 versus 1 break point.

5.2 Unit root test

Table 2 presents the results of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for three indices & four foreign exchanges, i.e. Sensex, Nifty, CNX 500, USD, GBP, Euro and Yen. All the variables were non-stationary at level; however the variables became stationary after logarithmic conversation & first differencing. This means all variables are integrated to order one, I (1), and the following Table-2 shows the result:

Augmented Dickey-Fuller						
H ₀ : variables has a unit root			H ₁ : variables are stationery			
Variable		t-Statistic	Prob.*	1%	5%	10%
Sensex	Intercept	-0.008487	0.9567	-3.432033	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-2.815215	0.1917	-3.960665	-3.411091	-3.127368
	None	1.387663	0.9591	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
Sensex(-1)	Intercept	-26.59671	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
Nifty	Intercept	-0.016249	0.9560	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-2.857063	0.1769	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368
	None	1.420932	0.9618	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
Nifty(-1)	Intercept	-26.48466	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
CNX 500	Intercept	-0.028311	0.9549	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-2.637876	0.2633	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368
	None	1.378172	0.9584	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
CNX 500 (-1)	Intercept	-25.85789	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
USD	Intercept	-0.650810	0.8568	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-1.342153	0.8770	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368

	None	0.979192	0.9139	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
USD (-1)	Intercept	-42.50179	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
GBP	Intercept	-0.624054	0.8629	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-1.485142	0.8348	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368
	None	1.016181	0.9191	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
GBP (-1)	Intercept	-39.08309	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
EURO	Intercept	-0.376711	0.9107	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-2.760324	0.2123	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368
	None	1.490398	0.9668	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
EURO (-1)	Intercept	-41.37458	0.0000	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151
YEN	Intercept	-0.944874	0.7743	-3.432034	-2.862169	-2.567149
	Trend & Intercept	-2.331331	0.4162	-3.960666	-3.411092	-3.127368
	None	0.470471	0.8164	-2.565624	-1.940915	-1.616639
YEN(-1)	Intercept	-61.01474	0.0001	-3.432042	-2.862173	-2.567151

5.3 Descriptive statistic

Table – 3

Stat. parameter	SENSEX	NIFTY	CNX500	USD	GBP	EURO	YEN
Mean	0.004928	0.005714	0.005880	47.57374	78.84925	58.71262	46.67748
Median	0.010785	0.012459	0.017794	46.33000	78.40000	57.85000	41.71000
Std. Dev.	0.186751	0.205442	0.214890	5.201109	8.463365	11.11339	9.959770
Skewness	-0.349995	-0.313988	-0.553947	1.438545	0.811866	0.334311	0.820414
Kurtosis	17.26251	10.49114	9.683935	5.515914	3.700586	2.867432	2.444571
Normality Test							
Jarque-Bera	29711.25	8234.206	6688.364	2128.431	455.6779	67.70036	437.2441
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Observations	3497	3497	3497	3497	3497	3497	3497

Interpretation:

Above table represents return and risk of the seven variables, in case of stock returns CNX 500 & GBP is the highest. Skewness and Kurtosis explains about symmetry and shape of the above distribution, as the skewness of Sensex, Nifty, CNX 500 are long tail to the left as the values are negatively skewed and in case of foreign exchange all long tail to the right are positively skewed. In case of kurtosis, three indices and foreign exchanges are greater than 3, which demonstrate its response from the impacts of any latest current affairs towards foreign exchange or stock market.

Jarque-Bera's p-value is far smaller than the significance level, so it doesn't conform to the normal distribution.

5.4 Lag order specifications

The first step involved while testing cointegration is to specify right number of lags. The results for various selection criteria are listed as under:

Table 4.1

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)
Included Observations = 3489 after adjustment
Series Included = SENSEX, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-43284.55	NA	41171.13	24.81488	24.82370	24.81803
1	-7999.193	70449.36	6.86e-05	4.602576	4.655519	4.621474
2	-7453.659	1087.628	5.09e-05	4.304190	4.401254	4.338836
3	-7143.352	617.7686	4.32e-05	4.140643	4.281827*	4.191038
4	-7049.920	185.7380	4.16e-05	4.101416	4.286720	4.167559
5	-6989.797	119.3503	4.07e-05	4.081282	4.310706	4.163174*
6	-6951.004	76.89730	4.04e-05	4.073376	4.346919	4.171016
7	-6920.731	59.92198*	4.03e-05*	4.070353*	4.388016	4.183741
8	-6902.997	35.05124	4.05e-05	4.074518	4.436301	4.203655

Table 4.2

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)
Included Observations = 3489 after adjustment
Series Included = NIFTY, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-43617.04	NA	49815.51	25.00547	25.01429	25.00862
1	-8319.329	70474.01	8.25e-05	4.786087	4.839031	4.804985
2	-7798.403	1038.567	6.20e-05	4.501807	4.598871	4.536454
3	-7592.202	410.5116	5.59e-05	4.397937	4.539121*	4.448332
4	-7500.589	182.1229	5.38e-05	4.359753	4.545056	4.425896
5	-7439.001	122.2573	5.27e-05	4.338780	4.568203	4.420671*
6	-7399.432	78.43501	5.23e-05	4.330428	4.603971	4.428068
7	-7371.497	55.29386*	5.22e-05*	4.328746*	4.646409	4.442134
8	-7355.381	31.85255	5.25e-05	4.333838	4.695621	4.462975

Table 4.3

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)
Included Observations = 3489 after adjustment
Series Included = CNX 500, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-43772.54	NA	54459.92	25.09461	25.10343	25.09776
1	-8476.714	70470.26	9.02e-05	4.876305	4.929249	4.895203
2	-7960.684	1028.806	6.81e-05	4.594832	4.691895	4.629478
3	-7755.661	408.1655	6.14e-05	4.491637	4.632821*	4.542032
4	-7664.424	181.3749	5.91e-05	4.453668	4.638972	4.519812
5	-7605.086	117.7928	5.80e-05	4.433984	4.663408	4.515876*
6	-7565.159	79.14357	5.75e-05	4.425428	4.698971	4.523068

7	-7538.291	53.18302*	5.74e-05*	4.424357*	4.742020	4.537745
8	-7521.109	33.96011	5.77e-05	4.428838	4.790621	4.557975

Interpretation:

Above test indicates lag length selection is based on LR test statistic at 5% level, Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC) and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ).

The system selection criteria selects 8 lags, SC selects 3 lags, HQ selects 5 lag and rest selects 7 lags. Here, this study adopted AIC and used 7 lags. This lag length selection process helps in reducing autocorrelation of the error terms and to increase the power of the test. Since the log-likelihood function is negative, the model is comprehensive.

5.5 Johansen Cointegration Test

Johansen Cointegration test is carried on as per the process outlined in methodology section. Results are presented in following three sections.

I. Cointegration Test Results indicating SENSEX with FOREX.**Table - 5.1**

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)
 Included Observations = 3489 after adjustments
 Trend Assumption = Linear deterministic trend
 Series Included = SENSEX, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 7

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
None *	0.118016	460.7225	69.81889	0.0001	Yes
At most 1	0.003170	22.56945	47.85613	0.9675	No
At most 2	0.002173	11.49174	29.79707	0.9481	No
At most 3	0.000910	3.903236	15.49471	0.9112	No
At most 4	0.000208	0.725741	3.841466	0.3943	No

The Trace Test in Table 5.1 indicates the existence of 1 cointegrating equation at the 5% significance level. This cointegrating equation has one linear combination among the variables that force the Sensex to have a relationship over time period, despite potential deviation from equilibrium levels in the short-term.

In order to confirm the results of the Johansen's Trace test, the results are also displayed about the Maximum Eigen value Test in **table 5.2** below.

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
one *	0.118016	438.1531	33.87687	0.0001	Yes
At most 1	0.003170	11.07771	27.58434	0.9634	No
At most 2	0.002173	7.588501	21.13162	0.9271	No
At most 3	0.000910	3.177494	14.26460	0.9342	No
At most 4	0.000208	0.725741	3.841466	0.3943	No

The Maximum Eigen value Test also shows 1 cointegrating equation at the 5% level confirming the Trace Test. Therefore these two tests confirm a cointegrating relationship over the sample period.

Table 5.3 – Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients(Standard errors in parentheses) [*t* statistics in brackets] Log likelihood 6914.281

SENSEX	USD	GPB	EURO	YEN
1.000000	-0.000477	0.000393	-0.000861	0.000639
	(0.00093)	(0.00067)	(0.00064)	(0.00062)
	[-0.51282]	[0.58311]	[-1.34484]	[1.02933]

Interpretation:

Since there is existence of 1 cointegrating equation, it can be said that a stable equilibrium relationship is present. The results are normalized on the SENSEX. Due to the normalization process, the signs are reversed to enable proper interpretation.

The USD and EURO are statistically significant according to the *t* values shown on the above table. The coefficients can be interpreted as follows:

- A 1% increase in the USD leads to a 0.00048% increase in the SENSEX in the long run
- A 1% increase in the EURO leads to a 0.00086% increase in the SENSEX in the long run

The GBP and YEN have negative relationships with the SENSEX, although only the YEN's '*t*' value indicates significance at the 5% level in the cointegrating equation.

II. Cointegration indicating NIFTY with FOREX**Table - 5.4**

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)

Included Observations = 3489 after adjustments

Trend Assumption = Linear deterministic trend

Series Included = NIFTY, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 7

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
None *	0.117710	459.5116	69.81889	0.0001	YES
At most 1	0.003168	22.56995	47.85613	0.9675	No
At most 2	0.002176	11.50096	29.79707	0.9478	No
At most 3	0.000910	3.898940	15.49471	0.9115	No
At most 4	0.000208	0.724053	3.841466	0.3948	No

The Trace Test in Table 5.4 indicates the existence of 1 cointegrating equation at the 5% significance level. This cointegrating equation has one linear combination among the variables that force the Nifty to have a relationship over time period, despite potential deviation from equilibrium levels in the short-term.

In order to confirm the results of the Johansen's Trace test, we also display the results of the Maximum Eigen value Test in **table 5.5** below.

Table 5.5

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
None *	0.117710	436.9417	33.87687	0.0001	Yes
At most 1	0.003168	11.06899	27.58434	0.9636	No
At most 2	0.002176	7.602017	21.13162	0.9264	No

At most 3	0.000910	3.174887	14.26460	0.9344	No
At most 4	0.000208	0.724053	3.841466	0.3948	No

Interpretation:

The Maximum Eigen value Test also shows 1 cointegrating equation at the 5% level confirming the Trace Test. Therefore these two tests confirm a cointegrating relationship over the sample period.

Table 5.6 – Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients(Standard errors in parentheses) [*t* statistics in brackets] Log likelihood 7366.666

NIFTY	USD	GBP	EURO	YEN
1.000000	-0.000508	0.000442	-0.000896	0.000658
	(0.00107)	(0.00077)	(0.00073)	(0.00071)
	[-0.47612]	[0.57164]	[-1.21916]	[0.92291]

Interpretation:

Since there is existence of 1 cointegrating equation, it can be said that a stable equilibrium relationship is present. The results are normalized on the NIFTY. Due to the normalization process, the signs are reversed to enable proper interpretation.

The USD and EURO are statistically significant according to the *t* values shown on the above table. The coefficients can be interpreted as follows:

- A 1% increase in the USD leads to a 0.00051% increase in the NIFTY in the long run
- A 1% increase in the EURO leads to a 0.0009% increase in the NIFTY in the long run

The GBP and YEN have negative relationships with the NIFTY, although only the YEN's *t* value indicates significance at the 5% level in the cointegrating equation.

III. Cointegration indicating CNX 500 with FOREX. Table - 5.7

Sample period (January 1, 2000 to June 30, 2014)

Included Observations = 3489 after adjustments

Trend Assumption = Linear deterministic trend

Series Included = CNX 500, USD, GBP, EURO, YEN

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 7

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
None *	0.106430	415.1869	69.81889	0.0001	Yes
At most 1	0.003167	22.56660	47.85613	0.9675	No
At most 2	0.002178	11.49964	29.79707	0.9479	No
At most 3	0.000910	3.893513	15.49471	0.9119	No
At most 4	0.000206	0.718556	3.841466	0.3966	No

Interpretation:

The Trace Test in Table 5.7 indicates the existence of 1 cointegrating equation at the 5% significance level. This cointegrating equation has one linear combination among the variables that force the CNX500 to have a relationship over time period, despite potential deviation from equilibrium levels in the short-term.

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen value	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Probability	Significance at 5% level
None *	0.106430	392.6203	33.87687	0.0001	Yes
At most 1	0.003167	11.06697	27.58434	0.9637	No
At most 2	0.002178	7.606123	21.13162	0.9262	No
At most 3	0.000910	3.174957	14.26460	0.9344	No
At most 4	0.000206	0.718556	3.841466	0.3966	No

The Maximum Eigen value Test also shows 1 cointegrating equations at the 5% level confirming the Trace Test. Therefore these two tests confirm a cointegrating relationship over the sample period.

Table 5.6 – Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients

(Standard errors in parentheses) [t statistics in brackets] Log likelihood 7532.392

CNX 500	USD	GPB	EURO	YEN
1.000000	-0.000879	0.000527	-0.001101	0.000924
	(0.00130)	(0.00094)	(0.00089)	(0.00087)
	[-0.67706]	[0.55979]	[-1.23246]	[1.06665]

Interpretation:

Since there is existence of 1 cointegrating equation, it can be said that a stable equilibrium relationship is present. The results are normalized on the CNX 500. Due to the normalization process, the signs are reversed to enable proper interpretation.

The USD and EURO are statistically significant according to the *t* values shown on the above table. The coefficients can be interpreted as follows:

- A 1% increase in the USD leads to a 0.00088% increase in the CNX 500 in the long run
- A 1% increase in the EURO leads to a 0.0011% increase in the CNX 500 in the long run

The GBP and YEN have negative relationships with the CNX 500, although only the YEN's *t* value indicates significance at the 5% level in the cointegrating equation.

Conclusion:

The study considers seven variables which include major India's stock indices & four major foreign exchanges. To examine the relation among the variables, Johansen cointegration technique is applied and found that USD and EURO has some disequilibrium with Sensex, Nifty and CNX 500. Further it can be noticed that this disequilibrium is less than 1% in case of USD, EURO and there is no significant relation among stock index, GBP and Yen. As Desislava (2005) noted, there is a weak relationship between exchange rate and stock market and also finds that a depreciation of the currency may depress the stock market, the stock market will react with less than one percent decline to a one percent depreciation of the exchange rate. This also implies that an appreciating exchange rate boosts the stock market⁶. It has been observed that the comparative returns of the three designated stock exchanges are minimal and in case of Foreign exchange, Great Britain Pound stands first, then Euro, USD and Yen in that order.

As per the result, investors can reduce their risk by investing in GBP as the returns are higher and not cointegrated with any of the designated stock exchanges in this study. So investors can diversify the risk with stock returns. The study finds that there is negligible long term relationship of stock returns [Sensex, Nifty, CNX 500] with USD, Euro and Yen.

⁶ Issues in Political Economy, Vol. 14, August 2005, The Relationship between Exchange Rates and Stock Prices: Studied in a Multivariate Model.

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